

USE OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS OF AUTOMATION OF PRODUCTION PROCESSES.

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***Abstract:** Disadvantages of the traditional approach to measurement uncertainty evaluation are analyzed. An algorithm for measurement uncertainty evaluation based on the Monte Carlo method is described, which makes it possible to eliminate these shortcomings. The results of a comparison of measurement uncertainty estimates obtained by the traditional method and the Monte Carlo method are presented. The need to revise the “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement” is substantiated and its current state is described.*

***Keywords:** measurement uncertainty, Monte Carlo method, revision of the “Guide to the Expressing of Uncertainty in Measurement”, kurtosis method.*

Successes achieved in the field of technologies are the basis for the creation of an industry of first-class importance for the technical development of the national economy, the development of the economy and culture of our independent country, as well as the well-being of the population [1].

Automation of production processes is one of the main directions of technical development, and it is considered the main factor that serves to continuously increase production efficiency, raise product quality to a higher level, reduce costs, improve working conditions, ensure safety in production, and protect the environment. Automation is increasingly entering scientific research, opening up new opportunities for the development of science and technology. In addition,

automation makes it possible to implement new, high-intensity processes that were previously unmanageable, to create new, effective materials unknown in nature [2].

When assessing the state and prospects of industrial automation, one should not be limited to the description of automatic control systems and technical means of automation, but the interrelated problems of the organization of automated production, management systems and tools, as well as the economy should be considered in a broad scope. It should be taken into account that automation is a continuously developing process, that it is inextricably linked with the specific characteristics of production and most fields of science and technology [3]. The dynamics of automation development is affected by a large number of legal and random factors: the state of technology and equipment and their readiness for automation, the quality and stability of raw materials, semi-finished products and energy resources, the qualifications of employees, the organization of the activities of workers and specialists, etc. [4].

Automation of technological processes and auxiliary services is related not only to the improvement of production techniques and the improvement of working conditions, but also to increasing the profitability of production, reducing the material and labor costs of a unit product, and increasing its technical and economic indicators..

Economic factors are the main factor in choosing an automation facility. There are many factors that increase the economic efficiency of automation in industry. In the current conditions, it will not be possible to achieve the economic efficiency of automation only by reducing the number of service personnel, because modern factories, workshops, divisions, sections are serviced by a relatively small number of people [5]. Therefore, the following factors can be included in the factors of increasing economic efficiency: increasing the quality of the product, reducing the consumption of raw materials and various energy, production waste, increasing the rhythm of production, increasing the production productivity, increasing the volume of output, improving the working conditions of service employees (life and health). in areas dangerous for) improvement at the expense of loss of harmful works [6].

Automation must be integrated with technology in new manufacturing plants being designed and envisioned. Economic efficiency is achieved as a result of carrying out a number of measures - activities, and it is evaluated as a whole for production and the enterprise; at these points, the independent economic evaluation of automation is often difficult, because it is combined with the general economic evaluation of the new production or enterprise [7,8,9].

Due to rapid technical development, "young" production "seeds" after a certain period and requires updating, including replacement of existing automation systems and tools with more modern and improved ones. There may be independent economic evaluations in the improvement of automation systems in existing production enterprises, as well as in the modernization of technology and equipment.

Due to the complexity and acceleration of technological processes, the management of modern production enterprises becomes effective only on the basis of extensive automation using microprocessor techniques and control computing techniques. Automation is most effective when the requirements for automation are taken into account at the stage of technological process design [10,11,12].

From what has been said, it follows that the scientific-technical and economic aspects of automation are of great importance in ensuring industrial development, raising the culture and standard of living of workers. However, an important condition for achieving success in industrial automation is the training of a large number of qualified personnel and specialists in control-measuring devices and automation, or who know this field as well as their own field, in institutes, design bureaus, and enterprises capable of solving production automation issues at a high scientific and technical level. .

Currently, the main purpose of the activities carried out in higher educational institutions of our republic is to fundamentally improve the quality of trained specialists. The main factor in the acceleration of these works is the integral connection of education, production and science [13,14,15]. At present, most of the countries of the world use the ISO system of sheep and goats. The ISO system was created to harmonize (as much as possible) international technical relations in

the metallurgical industry, to unify the system of national deposits and deposits. The purpose of moving to this is the necessity of specialization of industry in our republic, development of international trade and elimination of technical obstacles in it. This also ensures the increase in demand for our country's products in the world market. The State System of ISO's standards and standards is established on the basis of a strict single principle for general car details in our Republic [16,17,18]. To successfully solve the above-mentioned important tasks, highly qualified engineers are needed. It is necessary for such personnel to acquire radically new scientific ideas and the ability to solve high technical solutions. Acceleration of the national economy on the basis of scientific and technical progress is one of the most important tasks in the conditions of the market economy. Completing these huge tasks depends on the skills of the personnel.

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